

A Comprehensive Study on the Grey Area Dispute in the Bay of Bengal: Strategic Magnitudes of the Bangladesh–Myanmar–India Triangle and the Way Forward

Abu Hena Muhammad Yousuf^{a,*}

^a Associate Professor, Department of Oceanography, Faculty of Earth & Environmental Sciences, University of Dhaka; Honorary Research Fellow, International Centre for Ocean Governance (ICOG), School of Law, University of Western Sydney, NSW, Australia

*Corresponding Author: yousuf.ocn@du.ac.bd

ABSTRACT

The grey area in the Bay of Bengal among Bangladesh, Myanmar, and India poses challenges in defining boundaries and managing resources. In 2012 and 2014, ITLOS rulings settled significant portions of this issue between Bangladesh and Myanmar and between Bangladesh and India, respectively; however, ambiguities remain. Neighbouring countries' demands to control oil, gas, and fisheries pose a threat to the colossal depletion of maritime resources. In addition, their ambitions are to affirm sovereignty in the grey area, driven by the need for maritime security and territorial influence. Moreover, Bangladesh's objective is to protect these resources for both economic advancement and national defence by establishing transboundary negotiations. Proposals for joint development zones suggest a possible cooperative approach to fairly operating the grey area's resources, as well as fostering cooperation with Myanmar and India. This study aims to examine the strategic and legal positions of neighbouring countries concerning the grey area, focusing on their motives for asserting sovereignty and control over vital marine resources. The study finds that some realistic case studies' approaches are primarily driven by their desire to secure maritime resources for economic growth, ensure national security, and strengthen regional influence. This paper presents strategic plans to resolve the grey-area issue, aiming to manage and share resources equitably.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received:

10-09-2025

Accepted:

30-12-2025

KEYWORDS

Grey area; Bay of Bengal; Exclusive Economic Zones; Bangladesh; Myanmar; India.

1. Introduction

The Bay of Bengal (henceforth, it is BOB) covers 2.2 million square kilometres, bordered by

India, Bangladesh, Myanmar, and Sri Lanka. The disputed maritime area lies in the northern part of the bay. The "grey area" dispute over Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) and continental shelves in the BOB concerns

overlapping maritime claims among Bangladesh, Myanmar, and India. A grey zone in the context of maritime boundary delimitation refers to the situation where an area on one side of a maritime boundary is beyond 200 nautical miles (NM) from the state on the same side of the boundary but within 200 NM of the state on the other side of the boundary. This condition has created complicated legal and geopolitical challenges. The jurisdictions of these neighbouring countries are leading to competing demands over the valuable marine resources, such as oil, gas, and fisheries. The term "grey area" refers to the area where sovereignty claims are unresolved or contested, often due to differing interpretations of international maritime law (Kwiatkowska, 2013). Grey-zone operations, particularly in maritime contexts, can have significant strategic and economic implications for the future global order.

The grey area holds significant economic value due to its natural resources, although it is marred by legal complexities (Gao, 2019). Sea power protects trade, which is regulated by treaties; it is no accident that the father of international law, Hugo Grotius, was a seventeenth-century Dutchman who lived at the height of Dutch naval power worldwide. The value of grey areas extends beyond these complexities. The ramifications of this dispute are extensive, affecting not only regional stability but also the nation's respective economic growth (Hong, 2012). In the Dispute Concerning Delimitation of the Maritime Boundary between Bangladesh and Myanmar in the BOB, the International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea (ITLOS) narrated:

Such an area results when a delimitation line, which is not an equidistance line, reaches the outer limit of one state's exclusive economic zone

and continues beyond in the same direction until it reaches the outer limit of the other state's exclusive economic zone.

In 2009, Bangladesh initiated two separate arbitration proceedings against India and Myanmar under the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) concerning the delimitation of the Territorial Sea (TS), the EEZ, and the Continental Shelf (CS) in the BOB. While Myanmar and Bangladesh agreed to transfer their dispute to the ITLOS, an Arbitral Tribunal (AT) considered the case between India and Bangladesh (Suarez, 2016). The ITLOS delivered the judgment on March 14, 2012, while the AT rendered its award on July 7, 2014. These solved part of the conflicts between Bangladesh and its neighbouring countries, Myanmar and India, but there are still some ambiguities regarding the overlapping claims.

This research demonstrated Myanmar's and India's positions on legal and institutional strategies, diplomatic engagement, bilateral negotiations, economic and resource management initiatives, regional and multilateral cooperation, and strengthening domestic capacities to resolve this dispute. This research focuses on the grey-area dispute between Myanmar and India, describing their legal, economic, and strategic interests in the contested waters. Although several studies have examined the grey-area dispute in the BOB, a noticeable gap remains in research on Myanmar and India's positions and strategic plans to address the issue. While ITLOS's judgments in 2012 and 2014 clarified certain maritime boundaries among Bangladesh, Myanmar, and India, the literature has not sufficiently analysed how Myanmar manages the grey area, including its legal, diplomatic, and developmental strategies. There appears to be a lack of detailed studies on Myanmar and India's efforts to assert

their maritime rights, engage in bilateral negotiations with Bangladesh, and implement resource management or domestic capacity-building measures. This paper seeks to fill that gap by specifically exploring Myanmar's and India's strategic plans for resolving grey-area disputes.

2. Research Methodology

This research adopts a qualitative, doctrinal, and comparative legal methodology, suitable for examining both the textual interpretation and the practical application of international legal instruments concerning grey-area disputes among Bangladesh, Myanmar, and India. Moreover, the paper examines the existing literature on maritime boundary disputes and analyses the strategic, economic, and environmental interests of Myanmar and India. The study involves an extensive review of relevant international treaties, such as UNCLOS, and key judgments of the ITLOS. The data used in this paper will be collected from secondary sources, including academic articles, reports, and legal documents. The selected ITLOS cases, *Côte d'Ivoire vs. Ghana (2017)*, *Nicaragua vs. Colombia (2012)*, and *Romania vs. Ukraine (2009)*, were chosen for their relevance to overlapping maritime claims and equitable delimitation principles. The analysis is guided by the legal framework of maritime boundaries under UNCLOS, particularly Articles 56, 74, and 83, which define rights over EEZs and continental shelves. This framework provides a basis for evaluating Myanmar's and India's legal positions and the broader implications of the grey-area dispute in the BOB.

3. Historical Background of the Grey Area Dispute

The grey-area dispute arose from overlapping maritime claims among Bangladesh, Myanmar, and India concerning their EEZs and continental shelves in the BOB. The term "grey area" refers to regions where sovereignty claims remain unresolved due to conflicting interpretations of international law. There are three grey areas in the BOB. Two are bilateral, where the CS of Bangladesh overlaps with the EEZs of India and Myanmar. The third grey area is trilateral, where Bangladesh has authority over the CS, and the EEZs of Myanmar and India partially overlap (Bisen, 2022). To understand the origins of the issue between Bangladesh, India, and Myanmar, it is necessary to revisit the early territorial claims of these countries.

3.1 Myanmar-Bangladesh Maritime Disputes

The dispute over the maritime boundary demarcation between Myanmar and Bangladesh primarily stems from overlapping claims and interpretations of international maritime law, particularly under the UNCLOS. The first delimitation attempt occurred on May 9, 1966, with the Naaf River Boundary Agreement, which established a border along the Naaf River delta up to its mouth at the BOB. This agreement did not address broader maritime boundaries, leaving significant areas of the sea unresolved. On November 23, 1974, delegates from Bangladesh and Myanmar signed the Agreed Minutes, marking a significant step toward resolving maritime boundaries. A key feature was Special Chart 114, which illustrated a proposed boundary equidistant between the Myanmar Rakhine coast and St. Martin's Island (a territory of Bangladesh) (Balaram, 2012).

Renewed Dispute for Resource Discovery and Rising Tensions: In the early 2000s, significant

natural gas reserves were discovered in the BOB, increasing the strategic value of maritime claims. Bangladesh sought these resources to alleviate domestic energy shortages, while Myanmar aimed to export gas to China and India (Chawla, 2024). Like the 1974 document, the 2008 Agreed Minutes clarified key aspects, including the classification of islands under Article 121 of UNCLOS: i) St. Martin's Island was recognised as an "island" under UNCLOS; ii) Oyster Island, off Myanmar's coast, was excluded due to its ineptitude to support human settlement.

In October 2008, Myanmar deployed naval vessels to protect survey ships conducting exploratory drilling near contested areas, prompting Bangladesh to send naval forces and demand a halt to Myanmar's activities. Although the standoff ended without violence, the lack of resolution led Bangladesh to seek third-party arbitration under Annex VII of UNCLOS (Durai, 2025). *Annex VII Arbitration*: Annex VII arbitration involves a panel of five members, three of whom are jointly selected by the parties to the dispute. Myanmar chose not to pursue this route (ITLOS, 2011). *Transition to ITLOS*: both countries ultimately agreed to settle their dispute through ITLOS, reflecting the Tribunal's specialisation in maritime law and its capacity to provide a neutral, legally binding resolution (Huang & Liao, 2013).

Implications of Historical Developments: The evolution of this dispute underscores the dynamic nature of maritime boundary issues, which are often driven by resource competition and shifting national priorities. The resort to ITLOS arbitration underscores the role of international legal mechanisms in resolving disputes peacefully, even when bilateral negotiations fail. In brief, they reached an agreement on their territorial seas, setting a 12

NM limit. Nevertheless, this agreement did not mention the delimitation of EEZs and continental shelves. This led to subsequent conflict and overlapping claims, especially in areas rich in natural resources, such as oil and gas. Finally, this historical context of boundary delimitation sets the stage for understanding the Tribunal's judgment and its broader implications for international maritime law and state behaviour.

3.2 India-Bangladesh Maritime Dispute

This dispute is centred on the delimitation of the EEZ and the CS in the northern BOB. The conflicting claims resulted from different interpretations of the UNCLOS. The following sequence of incidents led to this arbitration. *Partition of India (1947)*: The Bengal Boundary Commission, chaired by Sir Cyril Radcliffe, established the boundary between India and East Pakistan (now Bangladesh). Ambiguities in maritime boundaries were left unresolved (Ranjan, 2018; Sufian, 2022). *Emergence of South Talpatty/New Moore Island*: In the early 1970s, a sandbar emerged at the mouth of the river separating India and Bangladesh. India referred to it as New Moore Island, while Bangladesh called it South Talpatty Island. Both nations claimed territorial rights over the island, escalating maritime tensions (Tanaka *et al.*, 2011). *Failed Bilateral Negotiations*: Multiple rounds of negotiations were held between 1974 and 2009 to delimit the maritime boundary. No consensus was reached, and tensions persisted (Huq, 2023).

India's 2008 incursion: Escalation of Tensions. Indian naval vessels escorted a survey ship into the disputed waters on Bangladesh's western border. Bangladesh again responded by sending warships to the area and defending its

sovereignty. The 2008 incidents with India and Myanmar heightened Bangladesh's concerns over sovereignty and resource rights in the BOB. The failures of bilateral discussions led Bangladesh to seek international arbitration (Datta, 2010). The historical resolution allowed both Bangladesh and India to explore and utilise marine resources, demonstrating the effectiveness of international legal mechanisms and fostering bilateral cooperation (Tanaka, 2015). The peaceful resolution set a precedent for managing similar disputes globally and emphasised the importance of equitable resource management, reinforcing regional stability and economic development (Choudhury, 2016; Islam, 2017).

The origin of maritime arbitration in the BOB stems from overlapping claims for EEZ and CS by bordering nations (India, Bangladesh, and Myanmar), fueled by the discovery of oil and gas reserves, complex coastal geography (like Bangladesh's concave coast), and disagreements over applying UNCLOS principles (like equidistance vs. equity) to delimit boundaries, leading to tensions and eventual arbitration cases, especially between Bangladesh and Myanmar/India in the late 2000s.

4. Principles and Methods of Delimitation

The fundamental tenet of both conventional and customary law regarding marine delimitation is that it must be accomplished through agreement. States must agree on maritime borders for them to be safe and stable (Nugzar, 2006).

4.1 Equidistance

The 1958 Territorial Sea Convention defines equidistance as

the line every point of which is equidistant from the nearest points of the baselines from which the breadth of the territorial sea of each of the two states is measured (Geneva Convention, 1958).

A comparable term can be found in the 1958 Convention on the Continental Shelf. This Convention applies the concept of equidistance exclusively to boundaries between adjacent States, and uses the term "median line" to refer to the equidistant line between opposing States. It appears that baselines along the coasts of the individual states whose offshore territories are to be divided by the boundary determine whether equidistance methods are used.

4.2 Equity and the equitable principle

Arbitral tribunals and the United Nations International Court of Justice (ICJ), 1982 made multiple attempts to define equality.

Equity as a legal concept is a direct emanation of the idea of justice. The Court is bound to apply equitable equity as a part of general international law. When applying positive international law, a court may choose among several possible interpretations of the law the one that appears, in light of the circumstances of the case, to be closest to the requirements of justice (ICJ, 1982).

The concept of *unicum*, which states that the geographical characteristics of each delimitation case vary so much that it is difficult, if not impossible, to propose any fixed principles applicable for the establishment of maritime boundaries between states, is closely related to the definition of equitable principles.

An equitable outcome took precedence over the equitable standards that the Court was compelled to adopt in 1982. They were only equitable because they enabled the court to reach a satisfactory conclusion. As a result, all generalisations had to be avoided, and the equitable principles had to be assessed in the specific context of the case:

It is the result that is predominant; the principles are subordinate to the goal. The equitableness of a principle must be assessed in the light of its usefulness for the purpose of arriving at an equitable result. Each continental shelf case [...] should be considered and judged on its own merits [...]. No attempts should be made here to overconceptualize the application of the principles (ICJ, 1982).

4.3 Single maritime boundary

States are increasingly using a single maritime boundary to split their maritime zones beyond the territorial sea for simplicity, predictability, and convenience since the emergence of the EEZ doctrine. When two states have nearby coasts, a line drawn seaward from the coast will often only divide the two states' territorial seas for the first twelve nautical miles. Beyond that, the two marine zones between states may be divided if they concur (Sharma, 1987). The Chamber of the Court took into consideration the fishing zone in the context of EEZ when it announced that, taking into account the growing number of states adopting an EEZ and the general demand for single delimitation in state practice:

It can be foreseen that with the gradual adoption by the majority of maritime states of an exclusive economic zone and, consequently, an increasingly general

demand for single delimitation to avoid as far as possible the disadvantages inherent in a plurality of separate delimitations, preference will henceforth inevitably be given to criteria that, because of their neutral character, are best suited for use in a multi-purpose delimitation (ICJ, 1982).

4.4 Proportionality

According to the theory, the length of each party's coastline and the ratio of the water and CS areas assigned to each party should be considered when determining maritime delimitation. As a result, the Court and tribunals must determine the approximate or precise lengths of the pertinent coastlines and compare that ratio to the ratio of the pertinent water and CS areas that have been temporarily delineated. Further analysis or adjustment would be considered if the fraction of the pertinent maritime zones does not roughly match the relative lengths of the coastlines (Charney, 1994).

4.5 Other methods

Another technique for establishing the maritime boundary between neighbouring shores is to draw a line perpendicular to the general direction of the coast. When neighbouring states have more or less straight coasts, the perpendicular line is more commonly used. However, a lateral delimitation based on a perpendicular line can only produce a mutually agreeable outcome if the overall direction of the coastline is quite apparent and the coast at the land frontier's termination is generally straight. The baseline sites are crucial for establishing the overall direction of such delimitation (Alexander, 1982).

The ideal method for defining the territorial sea is to adopt the equidistance/median line, as stated in Article 15 of the 1982 LOS Convention. A single line based on the equidistance approach appears to yield an equitable outcome for the CS and the EEZ beyond the territorial sea. To prevent an unfair outcome, it is crucial to identify the pertinent factors in the delimitation area that must be considered when shifting the equidistance line (Nugzar, 2006).

5. Evolution of Grey Area

The concept of 'grey area' became widely used when maritime delimitation disputes arose among the tri-states – India, Bangladesh, and Myanmar- and two judgements later in the BOB. Two noteworthy decisions in the cases of India-Bangladesh and Bangladesh-Myanmar maritime delimitation resulted in the introduction of a new terminology in maritime history- the 'grey area', a state of ambiguity that persists even after three years of adjudication.

Differing methods for delimiting maritime boundaries compounded the complexities of the grey area. To arbitrate the issue, Myanmar preferred the equidistance principle, while Bangladesh preferred the angle-bisector method. ITLOS finally addressed the issue, and in 2012, it delivered a judgment granting Bangladesh a 200 NM EEZ and a substantial section of the extended CS beyond 200 NM.

Table 1: Extent of Grey Area, BOB (Source: Magnússon, 2016)

Points	Latitude	Longitude
R-1	20°09'00"N	89°34'50"E
R-2	18°19'32.0"N	89°36'31.8"E
R-3	18°10'18"N	89°43'54"E
R-4	16°40'54"N	89°24'05"E

Figure 1: Grey Area Overlap: India and Myanmar (Source: Prerna & Pandey, 2018)

Bangladesh has also gained other important economic benefits from this verdict. The government can now start drilling for oil and gas within 200 NM and beyond 200 NM out to sea. Given Bangladesh's concave coastline, ITLOS applied the equidistance/relevant circumstances method in its judgment. Myanmar, presenting the equidistance principle in this case, accepted the Tribunal's judgment, which marked a peaceful resolution to the conflict. Regarding the conflict between Bangladesh and Myanmar, the ITLOS concluded that

The area, referred to by the parties as a 'grey area', occurs where the adjusted equidistance line used for delimitation of the continental shelf goes beyond 200 NM off Bangladesh and continues until it reaches 200 NM off Myanmar (ITLOS, 2011).

Following the 2012 ITLOS judgment in the Bangladesh-Myanmar case, the maritime boundary between Bangladesh and India remained unresolved. Bangladesh, therefore, brought a separate case against India to the Permanent Court of Arbitration (PCA), which delivered its verdict in 2014. The PCA largely upheld Bangladesh's claim to an equitable solution and granted it a 200 NM EEZ and a portion of the CS beyond that limit, similar to the ITLOS ruling (ICGJ, 2014). It is of particular importance to note that the sovereign rights of the coastal state over the EEZ are essentially limited to economic exploration and exploitation (*limitation ratione materiae*). However, when the two judgments, the 2012 ITLOS decision (Bangladesh–Myanmar) and the 2014 PCA decision (Bangladesh–India), were plotted on maps, their outer CS boundaries did not perfectly align at the point where the three countries' maritime zones meet in the deep sea.

This mismatch created a small overlapping zone, now referred to as the "grey area". The grey area lies beyond Bangladesh's 200 NM EEZ but within its CS claim, overlapping with the EEZs of India and Myanmar. This means that, legally, Bangladesh has rights to the seabed of CS in that zone, while India and Myanmar claim rights to the water column of EEZ above it. As a result, the grey area represents a rare and complex situation under international law, in which different layers of the sea are subject to different jurisdictions. Although it does not pose an active conflict today, it remains a technical and legal ambiguity arising from the differing outcomes of the two international judgments (Alam & Faruque, 2010).

The establishment of a "grey area" that could result in overlapping rights for Bangladesh, Myanmar, and India, despite Myanmar's non-participation in the latter arbitration, was one

such consequence of that ruling (Agarwal, 2010). The Tribunal generated further ambiguities regarding sovereign rights in this grey area while crafting the judgment in the Bangladesh/India case. To achieve fair outcomes for all parties, the Tribunal strongly urged the parties to cooperate regarding these sovereign rights, citing multiple instances of concurrent sharing of maritime territories (Mishra, 2016). The Tribunal urged the states to determine whether additional agreements or discussions were necessary to create a cooperative accord in this area (Magnusson, 2016).

6. Legal Framework of Maritime Boundaries

UNCLOS 1982 serves as the primary legal basis for maritime boundaries. Article 56 of UNCLOS gives coastal states the sovereign rights over their EEZs, which extend up to 200 NM from the baseline. Article 74 delimits the EEZs of states with overlapping claims and provides an equitable method for resolving disputes over such claims. Article 83 addresses the delimitation of the CS. Although UNCLOS should not be considered a self-contained regime due to its various ways of drawing on and looking to other rules of international law, the mechanisms available within UNCLOS should be considered a starting point for redressing violations of rights enshrined in that treaty (Lowe & Tzanakopoulos, 2012).

The fact, then, that cases on the law of the sea will often fall to be decided by international courts and tribunals should come as no surprise. The judgment of ITLOS in 2012 in the Bangladesh-Myanmar dispute employed the equidistance/relevant circumstances method, taking into account the curved shape of

Bangladesh's coastline. The judgment granted Bangladesh a 200 NM EEZ and a part of the outer CS beyond 200 NM. It also adjusted Myanmar's claim accordingly. Myanmar acknowledged the Tribunal's decision to solve the dispute peacefully.

Besides UNCLOS, bilateral agreements such as the 1986 India-Myanmar Agreement on maritime boundaries in the BOB and the Andaman Sea help prevent overlapping claims. Joint Development Agreements (JDAs), such as JDAs between Timor-Leste and Australia, also address legal solutions by permitting shared resource management in disputed areas (Klein, 2020). Regional frameworks such as the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) and the BOB Initiative for Multi-Sectoral Technical and Economic Cooperation (BIMSTEC) support political efforts to resolve conflicts and nourish collaboration (Davenport, 2014). This provides alternative dispute-resolution mechanisms and facilitates agreements on maritime boundaries.

Figure 2: Maritime zone under UNCLOS (NOAA, 2025)

7. Bangladesh vs. Myanmar's Overlapping Maritime Claims

The "grey area" dispute between Myanmar and Bangladesh in the BOB stems from overlapping maritime claims arising from the 2012 ITLOS judgment. Myanmar's claim to the grey area is

built on legal, geographical, economic, and strategic considerations. This paper extends the arguments in favour of Myanmar's claim, grounded in international law and practical realities. It is noteworthy that the maritime boundary between India and Myanmar does not encompass such a grey area. The 1986 agreement provided a clear demarcation, effectively preventing the emergence of overlapping claims or ambiguities between the two countries.

The grey area between Bangladesh and Myanmar emerged due to overlapping maritime jurisdictions following international tribunal rulings. It lies where Bangladesh's extended CS beyond 200 NM overlaps with Myanmar's EEZ within 200 NM. According to UNCLOS, Bangladesh has sovereign rights over the seabed and subsoil, as stipulated in Article 76, while Myanmar has rights over the water column and its resources, as outlined in Article 56 (Alam, 2012). This overlap creates legal ambiguity because both countries exercise control over different layers of the same maritime space, and UNCLOS provides no clear guidance on how to manage overlapping rights. As a result, the zone remains a legally and practically complex area for resource exploration and jurisdiction. Myanmar's position is that within its EEZ (up to 200 NM), its sovereign rights take precedence over Bangladesh's seabed rights, as the EEZ is a primary zone of jurisdiction. Myanmar claims that the ITLOS judgment relied too heavily on the equidistance principle, which does not fully account for the natural prolongation of Myanmar's land territory into the grey area. Myanmar argues that this approach ignores the specific geological and geomorphological realities of the BOB. For Myanmar, the natural prolongation principle underscores its rightful claim to the seabed in the grey area, as the

geological evidence indicates that the grey area lies closer to Myanmar's continental margin than to Bangladesh's. This argument seeks to align Myanmar's claim with earlier legal precedents, such as the North Sea CS cases, which emphasised natural prolongation over equidistance in cases of overlapping claims.

Figure 3: Bangladesh-Myanmar ITLOS Judgment (ITLOS, 2011)

Next, ITLOS outlined the legal framework of the grey area:

The Tribunal notes that the boundary delimiting the area beyond 200 NM from Bangladesh but within 200 NM of Myanmar is a boundary delimiting the continental shelves of the parties, since in this area only their continental shelves overlap. There is no question of delimiting the exclusive economic zones of the Parties, as there is no overlap of those zones (ITLOS, 2011).

Furthermore,

In the area beyond Bangladesh's exclusive economic zone that falls within Myanmar's exclusive economic zone, the maritime

boundary delineates the parties' rights with respect to the seabed and subsoil of the continental shelf. However, it does not otherwise limit Myanmar's rights with respect to the exclusive economic zone, NO particularly those related to the superjacent waters (ITLOS, 2011).

8. International Tribunal for the Law of the ITLOS Case Laws

ITLOS is resolving maritime boundary conflicts by applying the articles of UNCLOS to assure equitable and peaceful solutions (Mémoires, 2024). Key case law of ITLOS, particularly cases involving overlapping claims, has notably shaped the interpretation of international and maritime law.

8.1 Bangladesh/Myanmar (2012) – Maritime Boundary Delimitation in the BOB

Case Overview: The dispute between Bangladesh and Myanmar concerns overlapping claims in the BOB regarding EEZs and continental shelves.

ITLOS judgment: Considering the concave shape of Bangladesh's coastline, ITLOS applied the equidistance/relevant circumstances method. The judgment granted Bangladesh 200 NM of EEZ and a portion of the outer limit of CS beyond 200 NM (Anderson, 2012).

Impact: The judgment resolved the dispute, and Myanmar accepted the decision but kept its claim over the grey area. This case established a notable precedent for resolving overlapping claims in the EEZ through equitable methods (Bisen, 2022). In the ITLOS judgement, the delimitation of the CS resulted in an area

beyond 200 NM from the coast of Bangladesh but within 200 NM of the coast of Myanmar, on the Bangladesh side of the delimitation line (ITLOS, 2012).

This grey area resulted in an overlap zone where Myanmar's EEZ rights in the water column intersected with Bangladesh's CS rights on the seabed (Figure 4). The ITLOS termed the grey area arising as "a consequence of delimitation" and stated that "there are many ways in which the Parties may ensure the discharge of their obligations in this respect, including the conclusion of specific agreements or the establishment of appropriate cooperative arrangements" (ITLOS, 2012).

Figure 4: Bangladesh–Myanmar Grey Area (ITLOS, 2012)

8.2 Bangladesh/India (2014) – Maritime Boundary Delimitation in the BOB

Case Overview: The dispute between Bangladesh and India concerns overlapping claims in the BOB regarding EEZs and continental shelves (Shah, 2013). First, Bangladesh argued that the Bengal Delta's extremely unstable shoreline constituted a "special circumstance" warranting adjustment of the temporary equidistance line. Although the arbitral panel recognised the instability of the coastline, it did not view this as a pertinent factor that warranted changing the provisional equidistance line. Second, Bangladesh claimed that one pertinent factor was the "double concavity" of its coastline. The arbitral panel found that the provisional equidistance line had a "cut-off effect" on the seaward projections of Bangladesh's coast due to the concavity of the shoreline. The arbitral tribunal determined that this situation required the provisional equidistance line to be adjusted in Bangladesh's favour. Lastly, Bangladesh contended that the preliminary equidistance line needed to be further adjusted due to its people's reliance on fishing in the BOB (Burke, 2014).

The arbitral tribunal concluded that Bangladesh had not provided sufficient evidence of its reliance on BOB fishing to justify any modification of the provisional equidistance line. To prevent a cut-off effect caused by the concavity of Bangladesh's coast, the arbitral tribunal used the same technique both within and beyond the 200 NM limit, replacing the provisional equidistance line with a straight line. The Tribunal determined that no modification of the adjusted equidistance line was necessary at the end of the delimitation process, having evaluated the proportionality of the distribution of maritime zones in relation to the region's overall topography (Ramnath, 2022).

ITLOS judgment: The PCA ruled in Bangladesh's favour, granting it a larger share of the disputed waters. The Tribunal established the maritime boundary on the basis of equitable principles, taking into account the geographical features and the rights of both nations.

Impact: The judgment prompted India's claim to the "Grey Area" in the BOB, which involves complex maritime boundary delimitation issues, particularly regarding the EEZ and the CS beyond 200 nautical miles (Overfield, 2020). India's position is based on the principle of equidistance, which establishes boundaries by using fixed points equidistant from the baselines of the two countries. The geopolitical map shows that the grey area lies within 200 nautical miles of the Indian EEZ (Paleri, 2013). So, according to UNCLOS, Article 57, India's maritime territory has the sovereign rights over waters superjacent to the seabed and of the seabed and its subsoil with freedom to explore and exploit, conserve and manage the natural resources, whether living or nonliving, along with the production of energy from the water, currents, and winds. Regarding the separation of rights in the grey area, the ITLOS continued to observe that,

There are many ways in which the parties may ensure the discharge of their obligations in this respect, including the conclusion of specific agreements or the establishment of appropriate cooperative arrangements. It is for the parties to determine the measures that they consider appropriate for this purpose (ITLOS, 2012).

Therefore, the "grey areas" in the BOB, where one state may control the seabed (continental shelf) and another the water column (EEZ resources), present special governance issues

due to the disparity between EEZ entitlements (distance-based) and delimitation lines (equity-based). The grey area in the BOB has an approximate area of 1100 km² (AT, 2014). The Tribunal lacked the authority to compel the parties to reach a mutual understanding or agreement regarding this grey area, and even if it had, such an agreement would have amounted to coercion, as it must be achieved voluntarily rather than under duress (Schofield, 2013). The Tribunal recognised that the two states' distinct jurisdictions over the same area were a significant factor, as any delimitation would entail various legal and practical complications (ITLOS, 2011). Moreover, the overlapping boundaries between the water column and the seafloor are much more complex and can lead to numerous complications. Underwater sea expeditions may provide challenges.

Figure 5: Bangladesh–India Grey Area (AT, 2014)

The locations of various oil and gas-related structures may have an impact on the other state’s EEZ. The same holds for scientific studies conducted in maritime environments. The Timor Sea agreements have addressed them, although there are still several concerns about their sufficiency (Herriman & Tsamenyi, 1998). The collaboration of the relevant parties is crucial to these arrangements. (Kaye, 1998). Therefore, the nations will have to address the grey area issue once more, following years of diplomatic efforts to resolve the maritime delimitation disagreement.

8.3 The Jeopardies of a ‘Grey Area’ Jurisprudence in BOB

Owing to the limited international jurisprudence on CS delimitation beyond 200 NM and the fact that limits and definitions for delimiting the CS were not articulated with exactness by the involved parties as specified in the UNCLOS, the Tribunal took note of the delimitation rationale used in the 2006 Barbados vs. Trinidad (International Arbitral Awards, 2006) and Tobago arbitration (Kwiatkowska, 2007; Riesenber, 2012), which was subsequently noted in the Myanmar vs. Bangladesh and the Nicaragua vs. Colombia cases (Gómez-Pulisich, 2016; Tanaka, 2024). The tribunal followed judicial precedent, relying on UNCLOS Article 77, to hold that there is a single CS with no distinction between the CS within and beyond the 200 NM limit (Kunoy, 2022). The tribunals decided to recognise the duality of entitlements among countries as a practical consequence of the arbitrations, thereby leading to the Grey Area (Keyuan, 2000). In both cases, the tribunals refused to comment on the relative primacy of the EEZ or the CS in the Grey Area. The Grey Area, approximately 545 km² (187.5 sq km), can be

further disaggregated into three smaller zones (Table 2 and Figure 6).

Table 2: Disaggregated details of the BOB’s Grey Area (Mishra, 2016)

Zone	Country	EEZ	CS	Remarks
Zone Z1	India	213 NM ² (730 km ²)	Nil	Shared with Bangladesh CS entitlement
Zone Z3	Myanmar	271 NM ² (730 km ²)	Nil	Shared with Bangladesh CS entitlement
Zone Z2	Overlapped India & Myanmar	64 NM ² (215 km ²)	Nil	Shared with Bangladesh CS, India, and Myanmar EEZ entitlement
	Bangladesh	Nil	545 NM ² (1875 km ²)	Shared with India and Myanmar EEZ entitlement

The resultant murky situation is that Bangladesh has rights over the CS of the grey area, while both India and Myanmar have rights over the water column in the same grey area due to their sovereign rights over the same EEZ (Nguyen, 2017). This ‘double grey area’ is undoubtedly an extraordinary situation and one that has the potential to become a source of tension and conflict among the parties involved (Arrese, 2021). The Tribunal declared:

The Tribunal’s delimitation of the parties’ exclusive economic zones and the continental shelf within and beyond 200 nautical miles gives rise to an area that lies beyond 200 nautical miles from the coast of Bangladesh and within 200 nautical miles of the coast of India, yet it lies to the east of the Tribunal’s delimitation line. The resulting ‘grey area’ is a practical

consequence of the delimitation process. Such an area will arise whenever the entitlements of two states to the continental shelf extend beyond 200 nm and relevant circumstances call for a boundary at other than the equidistance line at or beyond the 200 nm limit to provide an equitable delimitation (ITLOS, 2011).

The tribunal, however, mindful of the potential conflicts that may occur as a result of the double grey area, did advise the parties that they must cooperate and act in tandem with one another to ‘ensure that each can exercise its rights and perform its duties within this area’ (Rao, 2014). However, this could be considered a lethargic approach to judicial decision-making in resolving a conflict; one cannot create more potential conflicts and rely on the already conflicted parties to cooperate (Goswami, 2014). The arbitral tribunal concluded that:

Within the area beyond 200 nm from the coast of Bangladesh and within 200 nm of the coast of India, the boundary identified by the Tribunal delimits only the Parties’ sovereign rights to explore the continental shelf and to exploit the “mineral and other non-living resources of the seabed and subsoil together with living organisms belonging to sedentary species” as set out in article 77 of the Convention. Within this area, however, the boundary does not otherwise limit India’s sovereign rights to the exclusive economic zone in the superjacent waters (ITLOS, 2012).

The double grey area in allocating the continental shelf rights to one country and the superjacent water rights to two other neighbouring countries creates a situation like saying that one cannot touch the branches and trunk of the tree but can pluck the leaves of it

(Prerna & Pandey, 2018), even though the Tribunal defends the creation of the grey area by locating the possibility of such a grey area in the arts. Articles 56, 58, 78, and 79 of UNCLOS (Award (n 5) 156 [507]) and thereby provide a legal justification for it. It is also true that such a grey area ‘is easy to conceptualise but very hard to put into practice’ (Gaja, 2024). Thus, the Tribunal, in this case, much like ITLOS in *Bangladesh vs. Myanmar*, in creating a grey area as an inevitable by-product of a much-needed and necessary equitable solution (Magnússon, 2013), might have been too ‘overly sanguine and optimistic’ (Schofield *et al.*, 2013).

Figure 6: Detailed depiction of the BOB Grey Area (India–Bangladesh PCA Award, 2014; Mishra, 2016)

Without question, the Tribunal’s strategy for resolving the problem of defining the territorial sea from a non-equidistant starting point was reasonable and consequential in light of

previous judgments as well as the subtleties of Article 15 of the LOS Convention. These aspects of the award were deemed realistic and were agreed upon unanimously.

The problem emerged when examining the Tribunal's process for defining the continental shelf and EEZ. The rationale for the delimitation line was unclear, despite its being established in accordance with previous norms. It should be noted that although the Tribunal was very careful to provide detailed justifications for its acceptance of jurisdiction in both cases, its justification for using the delimitation approach was insufficient. For example, it is unclear why the Tribunal selected the azimuth of 177°30' to circumvent the cut-off effect. When it comes to handling such cases, this award now reflects uncertainty and unpredictability in specific ways. Most significantly, future reservations from the states concerned in the BOB will result from the establishment of multiple grey areas. Although states in comparable circumstances have previously agreed to "joint areas" being utilised for a specific purpose and subject to the proper maritime system for its control, no such agreements or actions have been taken in this context.

8.4 Ghana/Côte d'Ivoire (2017) – Delimitation of the Maritime Boundary in the Gulf of Guinea

Case Overview: The dispute concerns the maritime boundary between Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire in the Gulf of Guinea, specifically regarding oil- and gas-rich waters.

ITLOS judgment: ITLOS employed the equidistance method and also considered special circumstances, such as the effects of past agreements and the proximity of the coastal cities.

Impact: The judgment underscored the importance of equitable delimitation, emphasising ITLOS's role in resolving resource-related disputes while balancing legal principles and practical considerations.

8.5 Nicaragua vs. Colombia (2012)- Maritime Boundary in the Caribbean Sea (CJ, Report, 2012)

Case Overview: Nicaragua and Colombia sought sovereignty over the Providencia Archipelago, San Andrés, and the surrounding maritime areas in the Caribbean Sea (Otero, 2014).

ITLOS judgment: ITLOS granted Nicaragua rights to the waters surrounding the archipelago while upholding Colombia's sovereignty over the islands (Pichel, 2024).

Impact: This case illustrates ITLOS's role in resolving disputes over island sovereignty and adjacent maritime zones. It also set precedents for resolving maritime delimitation disputes in island territories.

8.6 Serpentine Island (Romania vs. Ukraine, 2009)

Case Overview: Romania and Ukraine clashed over ownership of Serpentine Island.

ITLOS judgment: ITLOS applied the principle of equity to assure a just division of maritime space and ruled that the island had not had a significant effect on the delimitation.

Impact: This case highlights the importance of considering the size and relevance of islands when establishing maritime boundaries.

These cases emphasise ITLOS's assurance to solve maritime disputes through the application of equitable principles under UNCLOS and legal interpretation (Till, 2022). The Bangladesh/Myanmar case highlights the

Tribunal's role in clearing the complications of overlapping EEZ claims in disputed waters.

9. Case Studies of Similar Grey Area Disputes

Overlapping claims in grey areas have led to legal challenges in some international maritime disputes. These case studies demonstrated how similar disputes can also be resolved and propose insights for the Bangladesh-Myanmar dispute.

9.1 South China Sea Disputes

China, the Philippines, Vietnam, and Malaysia have overlapping claims in the South China Sea, a resource-rich area (Ndi, 2016). It has significant geopolitical importance. Access to fishing stocks and hydrocarbon resources is the driving force behind the conflicting claims over EEZs, CS, and territorial waters (Ndi, 2016). The PCA gave a judgment that favoured the Philippines and rejected China's claims based on the "Nine-Dash Line" (Chansoria, 2020). China, on the other hand, disapproved of the 2016 arbitration decision between the Philippines and China. In incidents involving the BRP Sierra Madre (Second Thomas Shoal), the Hai Yang Shi You 981 (oil rig into waters near the Paracel Islands) in 2014, the Natuna Islands in Indonesian waters in 2016, and the Whitsun Reef in 2021, China has been accused of employing grey-zone tactics and its maritime militia (Cheng, 2024; Sarjito, 2024). This case demonstrated the complexities of grey areas in strategic and resource-rich waters.

9.2 East China Sea

The discovery of possible hydrocarbon (oil and natural gas) deposits in the Senkaku/Diaoyu Islands in the East China Sea, which has heightened tensions between China and Japan, is a leading cause of the conflict and exemplifies classic overlapping EEZ claims (Midford & Østhagen, 2024). China and Japan both formalised their claims in the 1970s, following a 1969 United Nations assessment that identified possible oil and gas resources beneath the seabed near the islands. Divergent interpretations of UNCLOS underpin the maritime dispute. Japan supports the median line principle, which calls for drawing a border that is equally spaced between the coasts of the two nations (Ogunnoiki, 2020). Based on the natural extension of its continental shelf to the Okinawa Trough, China asserts that its EEZ extends farther east. The Chunxiao (also known as Shirakaba) gas field is a significant flashpoint. China's side of Japan's proposed median line is where this field is located; however, Japan believes that drilling there might access a common reserve that extends into the disputed area on the Japanese side of the line (Sato *et al.*, 2022). The grey area is still unanswered despite multiple encounters (Octafiyani & Vidi, 2023). It highlights the challenges of drawing maritime borders when islands are involved.

The success of international legal rulings under the UNCLOS actually depends on states' political willingness to cooperate and engage in cooperative diplomacy. There are legal boundaries in the "grey areas" of the BOB, but resource management and governance are still complicated. Despite being a significant legal win for the Philippines, China flatly rejected the South China Sea ruling, underscoring the absence of a central enforcement mechanism under international law. The East China Sea experience demonstrated that while the law provides the framework, genuine political

commitment to communication and actual cooperation is necessary for peaceful coexistence. A combination of political diplomacy and legal clarity is necessary for regional stability. Therefore, to manage their shared maritime area and prevent potential meddling by extra-regional powers, the BOB countries should prioritise consistent, sincere diplomatic engagement and confidence-building measures, rather than relying solely on legal rulings.

10. Barents Sea

A 67,000-square-mile "grey area" in the Barents Sea, renowned for its abundant fishing grounds and hydrocarbon potential (including oil and gas), was the subject of a decades-long maritime border dispute between Norway and Russia (Choi, 2014). When both countries reached a historic delimitation deal in 2010 that essentially divided the disputed region in half, the conflict was formally settled (Neumann, 2010). Since then, the agreement has facilitated cooperation between the two nations in oil and gas development and fisheries management in their respective new areas of focus. This case demonstrates the effectiveness of bilateral agreements in resolving grey area disputes, particularly those involving resource-rich zones (Hoel, 2012).

Legal decisions define fundamental rights in the "grey areas" of the BOB, such as the Barents Sea ruling; nonetheless, the practical difficulties of handling overlapping authorities require clear, bilateral cooperative agreements between the relevant governments. The parties involved were left to manage these areas in practice, in light of the legal findings. Without formal agreements, the "grey areas" cannot be effectively managed. Governments needed to create clear, transboundary operational

protocols. This covers the following protocols: i) resource management: determining how to manage "creatures of the shelf" (seabed resources) versus general fish stocks in the water column; ii) jurisdiction and permitting: a state cannot unilaterally authorise the construction of an oil platform without coordinating with the state that has water column jurisdiction, necessitating a shared approach to permitting and operation; iii) security and enforcement: creating a shared framework for maritime security and enforcement to prevent "grey zone activities" and potential conflicts. Lastly, although the court rulings established the main boundaries, the operational uncertainties of the grey areas remained unresolved. Sustained bilateral (or trilateral) talks, such as those that Norway and Russia have been holding for decades, are the answer. In summary, the Barents Sea case illustrates that a "grey area" is a legal concept that calls for a workable, cooperative diplomatic solution to ensure stability and shared economic advantage, rather than a perpetual impasse.

11. Gulf of Guinea

Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire have overlapping EEZ claims in the Gulf of Guinea, an area rich in oil reserves. The ITLOS resolved the dispute in 2017, establishing a boundary between the two nations (Mensah, 2023). All the parties' claims that the provisional equidistance line should be adjusted or shifted in this particular case due to pertinent factors like the concavity or convexity of the parties' coasts, the location of natural resources, and the parties' behaviour were rejected by the Special Chamber (CLCS, 1982). A unanimous, non-appealable ruling by the ITLOS Special Chamber on September 23, 2017, established a single maritime boundary for both

countries' territorial sea, EEZ, and CS. It concluded that, in this instance, an equitable solution was achieved by strictly applying the equidistance method.

Additionally, the Special Chamber settled in Stage 3 that the line it created "does not lead to an inequitable result owing to a marked disproportion between the ratio of the relevant maritime area allocated to each Party and the ratio of the respective coastal lengths" (Djokoto, 2023). The Tweneboa, Enyenra, and Ntomme (TEN) fields, among other economically significant oil and gas fields in the disputed area, are under Ghana's jurisdiction, according to the verdict (Ikporukpo, 2020). This case will remain an example of how ITLOS resolves grey-area conflicts by ensuring equitable access to resources. This decision emphasises that determining marine boundaries requires a combination of science and law, with geography taking precedence over resource-related factors, such as the existence and location of hydrocarbons (ITLOS, 2012).

Therefore, the conclusion of the Special Chamber of ITLOS for Ghana/Côte d'Ivoire, a clear, single maritime boundary that eliminates the ambiguity of a "grey area", is essential for maintaining peace and drawing investment for resource development in the BOB. In the end, Ghana's position prevailed because the single border line was established using a provisional equidistance line, and no "relevant circumstances" were found to support its modification. This suggests a uniform legal foundation for the BOB conflicts and supports the approach taken in the *Bangladesh vs. Myanmar* and *Bangladesh vs. India* judgments. Under UNCLOS Articles 74(3) and 83(3), states are legally obligated to engage in sincere negotiations to reach a fair resolution. To avoid endangering or impeding the final settlement,

states must make every effort to enter into Provisional Arrangements of a practical nature until a final agreement or verdict. To manage resources jointly in the interim, the BOB states might profit by formalising such agreements in areas where their interests intersect.

12. Myanmar's Strategic Interests in the Dispute

Myanmar's strategic interests in the grey-area dispute with Bangladesh centre on economic security, resource access, and national defence.

Resource Access: The grey area, rich in hydrocarbons and fisheries, is crucial for Myanmar's energy stability and economic growth. Controlling this area is crucial for Myanmar to meet its energy requirements and safeguard its resources for future development.

Energy Security: Offshore resources, particularly natural gas, are crucial for meeting Myanmar's energy needs. Ensuring control over the grey area allows Myanmar to reduce its dependency on neighbouring countries and enhance its energy security.

National Security: The grey area is located near Rakhine State, a key territory for Myanmar's national security. Gaining control over the area can ensure sovereignty and maritime defence, also keeping it safe from potential threats.

Geopolitical Influence: The BOB is significant for Myanmar due to its maritime trade routes and regional security implications. Gaining control over the grey area enlarged Myanmar's geopolitical standing.

Regional Cooperation: Myanmar seeks Joint Development Zones (JDZs) with Bangladesh to promote cooperative resource management

and peaceful resolution, thereby strengthening regional diplomatic ties.

13. India's Strategic Interests in the Dispute

India's strategic interests in the grey-area dispute with Bangladesh centre on maritime boundaries and EEZ security, resource exploration, strategic sea lanes, and regional influence.

Maritime boundary and EEZ security: India is concerned about the potential for Bangladesh's claimed maritime zones, particularly its baseline points, to encroach on India's EEZ in the grey area. Protecting its sovereign rights and resources is a primary concern, with a view to defending against piracy, Illegal, Unreported, and Unregulated (IUU) fishing, and trafficking.

Resource exploration: The dispute is fuelled by the prospect of valuable natural resources, including hydrocarbons, in the contested area. India plans to ensure access to these resources within its own EEZ (Arif, 2018).

Strategic sea lanes: The BOB is crucial for India's trade and economic prosperity, with approximately 95% of its trade by volume passing through the Indian Ocean. India is committed to securing these Sea Lines of Communication (SLOCs) to ensure the uninterrupted flow of trade and to protect its economic interests, which any instability in the region can indirectly impact.

Regional influence: India views the BOB as part of its strategic backyard, aiming to maintain a dominant security and economic presence in the Bay to counterbalance China's expanding footprint in the Indo-Pacific. For instance, it patronised the establishment of the Indian Ocean Rim Association (IORA) in 1997, which

has 21 member states and seven dialogue partners. Resolving the dispute with Bangladesh would enable India to focus on larger strategic issues and maintain its regional dominance.

14. Proposed Strategic Plan for Resolving the Grey Area Issue

The BOB holds significant geopolitical and economic value, particularly for countries like Bangladesh and its neighbouring countries, such as India and Myanmar, that rely heavily on its marine resources. Ambiguous jurisdiction hinders these regions' ability to fully utilise their maritime potential and maintain security in the disputed region (Hasan *et al.*, 2019). This article outlines strategic approaches to addressing the grey-area issue, focusing on legal, diplomatic, and developmental strategies. By leveraging international law, fostering regional cooperation, and strengthening domestic capacities, Bangladesh aims to mitigate the negative impacts of this dispute.

14.1 Legal and Institutional Strategies

Bangladesh's primary plan centres on clarifying and asserting its maritime rights within the framework of international law.

- a) **Utilisation of ITLOS Judgement:** Bangladesh acknowledges the binding nature of the ITLOS ruling and seeks to work within its framework. Its legal strategy includes ensuring compliance while simultaneously negotiating terms that favour sustainable resource management.
- b) **Domestic Legislative Reforms:** Bangladesh is working on refining its domestic maritime laws to align with international norms, such as the UNCLOS. These updates aim to strengthen

the country's legal standing in future negotiations and arbitrations.

c) **Engagement with Legal Experts:** Bangladesh has been consulting international maritime legal experts to assess its rights and obligations. This includes exploring potential avenues for legal clarification, particularly in areas where dual jurisdiction complicates enforcement.

14.2 Diplomatic Engagement and Bilateral Negotiations

Bangladesh recognises that resolving the grey area dispute requires constructive dialogue with Myanmar and India.

a) **Bilateral Talks:** Bangladesh has initiated several rounds of discussions aimed at establishing a cooperative framework for managing the grey area. These talks focus on striking a balance between resource-sharing arrangements and respecting concerns about sovereignty.

b) **Confidence-Building Measures:** To reduce tensions, Bangladesh is advocating for joint initiatives, such as joint naval patrols and shared monitoring systems, to address illegal activities in the disputed waters.

c) **Third-Party Mediation:** While Bangladesh prefers bilateral resolutions, it has expressed openness to third-party mediation by ASEAN or international organisations to facilitate agreements on contentious points.

15. Economic and Resource Management Initiatives

To mitigate the economic impact of the grey area dispute, Bangladesh is focusing on pragmatic resource management strategies.

a) **Joint Resource Development:** Myanmar proposes the establishment of JDZs in the grey area. These zones would allow shared exploration and extraction of undersea oil, gas, and other resources, ensuring mutual economic benefits.

b) **Fisheries Management:** Bangladesh is negotiating sustainable fishing agreements to regulate overfishing and illegal fishing activities. This includes establishing quotas, seasonal restrictions, and shared enforcement mechanisms.

c) **Investment Promotion:** To attract foreign investments in offshore energy projects, Myanmar is offering assurances regarding dispute mitigation and the security of investments in contested areas.

16. Regional and Multilateral Cooperation

Recognising the broader regional implications of the dispute, Bangladesh seeks to engage with regional organisations and frameworks.

a) **Engagement with ASEAN and BIMSTEC:** Bangladesh is leveraging its membership in regional organisations to promote dialogue on maritime security and resource sharing. This includes advocating for regional agreements on dispute resolution and joint development in overlapping EEZs.

b) **Marine Environment Protection:** Bangladesh is collaborating with regional actors to address environmental concerns in the BOB. Initiatives include shared efforts to combat

pollution, preserve biodiversity, and promote sustainable maritime practices.

c) **Capacity Building and Knowledge Sharing:** Bangladesh has partnered with neighbouring countries and international institutions to enhance its technical and enforcement capacities, particularly in areas such as maritime surveillance and ecological conservation.

16.1 Strengthening Domestic Capacities

Bangladesh's plans also involve enhancing its domestic capacities to assert its maritime rights effectively.

a) **Naval Modernisation:** Bangladesh is investing in the modernisation of its navy and coast guard to strengthen its ability to patrol and protect its maritime zones, including the grey area.

b) **Surveillance and Monitoring:** Advanced surveillance technologies, such as satellite systems and uncrewed aerial vehicles (UAVs), are being deployed to monitor activities in disputed waters.

c) **Community Engagement:** Bangladesh is engaging with coastal communities to promote sustainable fishing practices and reduce reliance on overexploited marine resources. This strategy aims to address the socioeconomic dimensions of the grey area dispute.

Finally, Bangladesh should continue to maintain a non-alliance foreign policy and promote multilateralism in BOB by being actively engaged in regional cooperative forums like the South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC), the Bangladesh, China, India and Myanmar Economic Corridor (BCIM), the Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Nepal (BBIN) Agreement, BIMSTEC, ASEAN, the IORA Indian

Ocean Naval Symposium (IONS) and so on. In addition, a high-level national committee should be constituted, comprising experts in security and international relations, to study and formulate guidelines and courses of action for protecting national interests. Manifestly, there is no quick and easy solution to these problems. However, one thing can indeed be concluded with confidence. Success will be unlikely in these grey-zone conflicts if the protagonists do not realise they are in one and act accordingly.

17. Conclusion

This study highlights that while the 2012 ITLOS and 2014 PCA judgments addressed key aspects of maritime delimitation between Bangladesh and Myanmar, as well as between Bangladesh and India, the grey area in the BOB continues to pose legal and strategic challenges. By focusing on Bangladesh's perspective, this research fills a critical gap in the literature, revealing how Bangladesh actively develops a comprehensive strategy to manage the grey area through legal, diplomatic, and developmental measures. The findings show that Bangladesh's approach, anchored in international law, bilateral negotiations with Myanmar and India, resource management initiatives such as JDZs and sustainable fisheries, and domestic capacity building, reflects a deliberate effort to protect its maritime rights while promoting regional cooperation. The conclusion underscores that resolving the grey-area dispute requires more than legal rulings; it necessitates a strategic, multidimensional approach that aligns national interests with international norms. Bangladesh's initiatives demonstrate the potential of combining lawful assertiveness with cooperative mechanisms to achieve equitable resource sharing, enhance maritime

security, and foster long-term stability in the BOB. By examining Myanmar's and India's strategies, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of state behaviour in overlapping maritime claims and provides practical insights for managing similar disputes in other regional contexts.

Source of Fund

The research was Self-funded.

Author Contribution

Conceptualisation, methodology, software, validation, formal analysis and investigation, resources, and data curation were done by Dr Abu Hena Muhammad Yousuf. Writing, review, and editing were done by Dr Abu Hena Muhammad Yousuf. The author has read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank the Bangladesh Navy for assisting with this research by providing datasets, and the Institute of the Bay of Bengal and Bangladesh Studies for the opportunity. I would also like to thank the School of Law at the University of Western Sydney, Australia, for its generous support in resolving the technical issues.

Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

References

Agarwal, S. K. (2010). India-Bangladesh Maritime Dispute: An International Law Perspective. *Maritime Affairs: Journal of the National*

Maritime Foundation of India, 6(1), 28-50. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09733159.2010.508241>

Alam, M. S., & Al Faruque, A. (2010). The Problem of Delimitation of Bangladesh's Maritime Boundaries with India and Myanmar: Prospects for a Solution. *The International Journal of Marine and Coastal Law*, 25(3), 405-423. <https://doi.org/10.1163/157180810x517015>

Alam, M. K. (2014). Delimitation of Maritime Boundary between Bangladesh and Myanmar by the ITLOS. *Northern University Journal of Law*, 3, 7-14. <https://doi.org/10.3329/nujl.v3i0.18380>

Alexander, L. M. (1983). Baseline delimitations and maritime boundaries. *Virginia, Journal of International Law*, 23(4), 503-536.

Anderson, D. H. (2012). Delimitation of the Maritime Boundary in the Bay of Bengal (Bangladesh/Myanmar). *American Journal of International Law*, 106(4), 817-824. doi:10.5305/amerjintelaw.106.4.0817

Arif, Md. K. H. (2018). Bangladesh-Myanmar Maritime Boundary Delimitation in the Bay of Bengal: An Analysis on the Development of International Law. *Kathmandu School of Law Review*, 53-64. <https://doi.org/10.46985/jms.v6i2.210>

Arrese, D. (2021). 'The Bay of Bengal Maritime Boundary Arbitration (Bangladesh and India), *Max Planck Encyclopedias of International Law* (November 2014), 3(1), 233-451. <https://opil.ouplaw.com/view/10.1093/law:epil/9780199231690/law-9780199231690-e2163>

AT. (2014). Area calculated using the Caris law of the Sea (LOTS) Geographical Information System (GIS) Software.

Balaram, R. A. (2012). Case Study: The Myanmar and Bangladesh Maritime Boundary Dispute in the

- Bay of Bengal and Its Implications for South China Sea Claims. *Journal of Current Southeast Asian Affairs*, 31(3), 85-104. <https://doi.org/10.1177/186810341203100304>
- Burke, N. (2014, September). Annex VII Arbitral tribunal delimits maritime boundary between Bangladesh and India in the Bay of Bengal. *American Society of International Law*. <https://www.asil.org/insights/volume/18/issue/20/annex-vii-arbitral-tribunal-delimits-maritime-boundary-between>
- Bisen, A. (2022). Enhancing maritime security in the Bay of Bengal: Resolution of Grey Areas between India, Bangladesh, and Myanmar. *Maritime Affairs: Journal of the National Maritime Foundation of India*, 1-30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09733159.2022.2097701>
- Chansoria, M. (2020). Arbitration as a Means to Settle Territorial Disputes in the South China Sea: Case Study and History of China and The Philippines. *Policy Brief*, 1-11.
- Charney, J. I. (1994). Progress in international maritime boundary delimitation law. *American Journal of International Law*, 88(2), 227-256.
- Chawla, A. K. (2024). *Maritime Power and China's Grand Strategy*. Taylor & Francis.
- Cheng, C. (2024). The paradox of protection: Defending against Grey Zone Attacks in an open society. *RAND Europe*.
- C.J. Reports. (2012). Territorial and Maritime Dispute between Nicaragua and Colombia in the Caribbean Sea, (2012): C.J. Reports 624, at paras. 190-194.
- Choi, Y. H. (2014). The Barents Sea: equal division of the disputed sea between Russia and Norway. *The Journal of East Asian Affairs*, 28(2), 61.
- Churchill, R. (2012). *The Bangladesh/Myanmar Case: Continuity and Novelty in the Law of Maritime Boundary Delimitation*. Cambridge International Law Journal, 1(1), 137-152. <https://doi.org/10.7574/cjicl.01.01.3>
- Choudhury, A. (2016). Maritime boundary disputes in the Bay of Bengal: Legal and geopolitical considerations. *Ocean Development & International Law*, 47(3), 205-230. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00908320.2016.1200437>
- CLCS. (1982). Article 76 and Annex II of the Convention on the Law of the Sea, Dec. 10, 1982, 1833 U.N.T.S. 397.
- Datta, S. (2010). Bangladesh's Extended Continental Shelf: Navigating the Course with India and Myanmar. *Strategic Analysis*, 34(5), 728-743.
- Davenport, T. (2014). Southeast Asian approaches to maritime boundaries. *Asian Journal of International Law*, 4(2), 309-357.
- Djokoto, G. (2023). *An Analysis of the Application of Maritime Delimitation Principles and Methods in the Ghana-Côte D'Ivoire Maritime Boundary Dispute* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Wollongong).
- Durai, S. (2025). Maritime Security in the Bay of Bengal Region. *Journal of Indian Ocean Studies*, 33(2), 177-187. <https://doi.org/10.32381/jios.2025.33.02.2>
- Geneva Convention. (1958). *Geneva Convention on the Continental Shelf*. Article 6.
- Gaja, G. (2024). Grey Areas in Maritime Delimitation. *The International Journal of Marine and Coastal Law*, 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718085-bja10202>
- Gao, J. (2019). The Delimitation Method for the Continental Shelf Beyond 200 Nautical Miles: A Reflection on the Judicial and Arbitral Decisions. *Ocean Development & International Law*, 51(2), 116-142. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00908320.2019.1668614>
- Gómez-Pulisich, F. M. (2017). *L'affaire Du Différend Territorial Et Maritime Entre Le Nicaragua Et*

- La Colombie: Certaines Questions Concernant La Souveraineté Territoriale Et La Délimitation Maritime. *International Law: Revista Colombiana de Derecho Internacional*, 14(28).
<https://doi.org/10.11144/javeriana.il14-28.ldtm>
- Goswami, A. (2014). The Award and its Implications. *Economic and Political Weekly*.
<https://www.epw.in/journal/2014/29/web-exclusives/award-and-its-implications.html>
- Hasan, M. M., Jian, H., Alam, M. W., & Chowdhury, K. A. (2019). Protracted maritime boundary disputes and maritime laws. *Journal of International Maritime Safety, Environmental Affairs, and Shipping*, 2(2), 89-96.
- Herriman, M., & Tsamenyi, M. (1998). The 1997 Australia-Indonesia maritime boundary treaty: A secure legal regime for offshore resource development?. *Ocean Development & International Law*, 29(4), 361-397.
- Hoel, A. H. (2012). The 2010 Norway-Russia Marine Boundary Agreement and Bilateral Cooperation on Integrated Oceans Management. *Nordlit*, 16(1), 15.
<https://doi.org/10.7557/13.2297>
- Hong, N. (2012). UNCLOS and ocean dispute settlement: Law and politics in the South China Sea. Routledge.
- Huang, Y., & Liao, X. (2013). Natural Prolongation and Delimitation of the Continental Shelf Beyond 200 nm: Implications of the Bangladesh/Myanmar Case. *Asian Journal of International Law*, 4(2), 281-307.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/s2044251313000301>
- Huq, M. E. (2023). Recent Issues and Problems in Bangladesh-India Relations: A Bangladeshi Perspective. *European Scientific Journal*, ESJ, 19(32), 9-9.
<https://doi.org/10.19044/esj.2023.v19n32p9>
- International Arbitral Awards. (2006). Arbitration between Barbados and Trinidad and Tobago Relating to the Delimitation of the Exclusive Economic Zone and Continental Shelf, 11 April 2006, U.N. Reports of International Arbitral Awards, Vol. XXVII, 147-251, at paras. 224-235.
- Ikporukpo, C. O. (2020). Boundaries and Natural Resources in the Sea: Oil, Boundary Disputes and the Militarization of the Gulf of Guinea. *The Journal of Territorial and Maritime Studies*, 7(2), 103-127.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/jtms.7.2.103>
- Islam, S. (2017). The Bay of Bengal maritime boundary disputes and their resolution: Implications for regional security and cooperation. *J. of International Affairs*, 71(2), 45-68.
<https://doi.org/10.1353/jia.2017.0003>
- ITLOS, "Dispute concerning Delimitation of the Maritime Boundary between Bangladesh and Myanmar in the Bay of Bengal (Bangladesh/Myanmar)," March 14, 2012, https://www.itlos.org/fileadmin/itlos/documents/cases/case_no_16/published/C16-J-14_mar_12.pdf (accessed March 28, 2022).
- ICJ. (1982). United Nations International Court of Justice (ICJ) judgment on 1982 Tunisia/Libya case. Online at: <http://www.icj-cij.org/icjwww/icasess/itl/itl_ijudgment/itl_ijudgment_19820224.pdf>. Accessed on 15 January 2007
- ICGJ. (2014). Bay of Bengal Maritime Boundary Arbitration (Bangladesh/India), Final Award of the LOSC Annex VII Tribunal (7 July 2014), International Courts of General Jurisdiction (ICGJ) 479, 7th July 2014, Permanent Court of Arbitration (PCA, 2014): Award (n 5) 156 [506]

- Kaye, S. (1998). The use of multiple boundaries in maritime boundary delimitation: Law and practice. *Aust. YBIL*, 19, 49.
- Keyuan, Y.-H. S., Zou. (2000). Maritime Legislation of Mainland China and Taiwan: Developments, Comparison, Implications, and Potential Challenges for the United States. *Ocean Development & International Law*, 31(4), 303-345.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00908320051058135>
- Klein, N. (2020). Responding to law of the sea violations. *Australian International Law Journal*, 27, 1-29.
- KUNOY, B. (2022). The Delimitation of Outer Continental Shelf Areas: A Critical Analysis of Courts' and Tribunals' Heterogeneous Approaches. *Canadian Yearbook of International Law/Annuaire Canadien de Droit International*, 59, 200-232.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/cyl.2022.15>
- Kwiatkowska, B. (2007). The 2006 Barbados/Trinidad and Tobago Award: A Landmark in Compulsory Jurisdiction and Equitable Maritime Boundary Delimitation. *The International Journal of Marine and Coastal Law*, 22(1), 7-60.
<https://doi.org/10.1163/157180807781475245>
- Kwiatkowska, B. (2013). Submissions to the UN commission on the limits of the Continental Shelf: the practice of developing states in cases of disputed and unresolved maritime boundary delimitations or other land or maritime disputes. Part one. *The International Journal of Marine and Coastal Law*, 28(2), 219-341.
- Lowe, VS., & Tzanakopoulos, A. (2012). The Development of the Law of the Sea by the International Court of Justice. *The development of international law by the International Court of Justice*, 177-193.
- Magnússon, B. M. (2016). The grey areas in the Bay of Bengal. *Indian Journal of International Law*, 56(1), 41-58.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40901-016-0033-4>
- Mémoires, P. VS. D. (2024). Pleadings, Minutes of Public Sitzings and Documents Mémoires, Procès-verbaux des Audiences Publiques et Documents. *18(1)*, 104-133.
- Mensah, G. B. (2023). Maritime Law: International Treaties, UNCLOS Principles, and Ghanaian-ivorian Petroleum Dispute. *IJFMR - International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 5(6).
<https://doi.org/10.36948/ijfmr.2023.v05i06.8504>
- Midford, P., & Østhagen, A. (2024). The East China Sea: A Case of Ocean Geopolitics and Maritime Conflict. *East Asia*, 41.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12140-024-09426-y>
- Mishra, R. (2016). The "Grey Area" in the Northern Bay of Bengal: A Note on a Functional Cooperative Solution. *Ocean Development & International Law*, 47(1), 29-39.
- NOAA. (2025). Maritime zones and boundaries. (n.d.) National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration.
<https://www.noaa.gov/maritime-zones-and-boundaries>
- Ndi, G. K. (2016). Philippines v China: assessing the implications of the South China Sea arbitration. *Australian Journal of Maritime & Ocean Affairs*, 8(4), 269-285.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/18366503.2016.1244142>
- Neumann, T. (2010, November). Norway and Russia agree on maritime boundary in the Barents Sea and the Arctic Ocean. In *The American Society of International Law* (Vol. 14, No. 34, pp. 1-4).
- Nguyen, L. N. (2017). UNCLOS TRIBUNALS AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE OUTER CONTINENTAL SHELF REGIME. *International and Comparative Law Quarterly*, 67(2), 425-454.

- <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0020589317000549>
- Nugzar, D. (2005). Delimitation of Maritime Boundaries between Adjacent States. The United Nations Nippon Foundation. https://www.un.org/depts/los/nippon/unnnf_programme_home/fellows_pages/fellows_papers/dundu_a_0607_georgia.pdf
- Octafiyani, E., & Vidi, M. (2023). Analysis Conflict Cause of Senkaku and Diaoyu Island Territory Dispute between China and Japan. *Indonesian Journal of Conflict and Peace Research*, 1(1), 1-12.
- Ogunnoiki, A. O. (2020). The East China Sea disputes: Examining China and Japan's territorial Claims. *African Journal of Law, Political Research and Administration*, 3(2), 79-92.
- Otero, M. (2014). Problems in the Caribbean: The absence of finality to the territorial dispute in Nicaragua vs. Colombia will have negative impacts in the region. *U. Tol. L. Revs.*, 46, 617.
- Overfield, C. (2020). Reflecting the Law of the Sea: In Defense of the Bay of Bengal's Grey Area. Center for International Maritime Security. <https://cimsec.org/reflecting-the-law-of-the-sea-in-defense-of-the-bay-of-bengals-grey-area/>
- Paleri, P. (2013). Maritime challenges and priorities in Asia: an Indian perspective. In *Maritime Challenges and Priorities in Asia* (pp. 272-283). Routledge.
- Pichel, C. (2024). Question of the Delimitation of the Continental Shelf Between Nicaragua and Colombia Beyond 200 Nautical Miles from the Nicaraguan Coast (Nicar. vs. Colom.) (ICJ). *International Legal Materials*, 63(3), 327-427.
- Prerna, R., & Pandey, D. K. (2018). The shades of grey over blue: A maritime delimitation dogma. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 158, 93-102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2018.03.027>
- Ramnath, K. (2022). Making Maritime Boundaries in the Bay of Bengal. *Law and History Review*, 40(3), 561-578. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0738248022000396>
- Ranjan, A. (2018). India-Bangladesh Border Disputes, 1947-2015. In *India-Bangladesh Border Disputes: History and Post-LBA Dynamics* (pp. 65-87). Singapore: Springer Singapore. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-8384-6>
- Rao, P.S. (2014). Bay of Bengal Maritime Boundary Arbitration between Bangladesh and India (<https://pca-cpa.org/cn/cases/18/>): Concurring and Dissenting Opinion of Dr. P. S. Rao, 01-23. <https://pcacases.com/web/sendAttach/384>
- Riesenberg, D. P. (2012). International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea: delimitation of the maritime boundary between Bangladesh and Myanmar in the Bay of Bengal (Bangladesh/Myanmar). *International Legal Materials*, 51(4), 840-915. <https://doi.org/10.5305/intelegamate.51.4.0840>
- Sato, Y., Chadha, A., De Souza, M., Coutaz, G., & Karalekas, D. (2022). Understanding the Senkaku/Diaoyu Islands dispute: Diplomatic, legal, and strategic contexts. *Asian territorial and maritime disputes: A critical introduction*, 48-64.
- Sarjito, A. (2024). China's Grey Zone Strategy in the South China Sea: Tactics, Objectives, and Regional Implications. *Indonesian Journal of Multidisciplinary Sciences (IJoMS)*, 3(2), 113-135.
- Schofield, C., Telesetsky, A., & Lee, S. (2013). A tribunal navigating complex waters: implications of the Bay of Bengal case. *Ocean Development & International Law*, 44(4), 363-388. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00908320.2013.808939>

- Shah, R. (2013). Bangladesh–Myanmar ITLOS Verdict: Precedence for India? *Strategic Analysis*, 37(2), 178–185. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09700161.2012.755782>
- Sharma, S. P. (1987). The single maritime boundary regime and the relationship between the continental shelf and the exclusive economic zone. *Int'l J. Estuarine & Coastal L.*, 2, 203.
- Suarez, S. VS. (2016). The Arbitral award in the Bangladesh/India Maritime Delimitation in the Bay of Bengal and Its Contribution to International Maritime Boundary Law: A Case Commentary. *Maritime Safety and Security Law Journal*, 2, 83.
- Sufian, A. (2022). India–Bangladesh Border Disputes: History and Post-LBA Dynamics. *Journal of Borderlands Studies*, 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08865655.2022.2046483>
- Tanaka, K., Aspect, I. C., & Overlap, I. E. C. (2011). Indo-Bangladesh maritime border dispute conflicts over a disappeared island. *ICE Case Studies*, (270).
- Tanaka, Y. (2015). Jurisdiction of States and the Law of the Sea. In *Research Handbook on Jurisdiction and Immunities in International Law* (pp. 110-150). Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Tanaka, Y. (2024). Recent Developments in the Jurisprudence Concerning the Delimitation of the Continental Shelf Beyond 200 Nautical Miles: Analysis of the Mauritius/Maldives and Nicaragua vs. Colombia Cases. *International Law Studies*, 103(1), 3.
- The Arbitral Tribunal (AT), "In the Matter of the Bay of Bengal Maritime Boundary Arbitration between the People's Republic of Bangladesh and the Republic of India," July 7, 2014, <https://pcacases.com/web/sendAttach/383> (accessed March 30, 2022).
- Till, G. (2022). Grey Zone Operations: The Rules of the Game. *IDSS Paper*. <https://rsis.edu.sg/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/IP22024.pdf>